

Keywords:

#data, #OpenScience, #FAIRprinciples,
#FAIRsharing, #FAIRdata #Trust, #FAIR indicators,
#EOSCinPractice

Enhancing FAIRness and TRUSTworthiness in the REPOPSI open repository

Leveraging EOSC and RDA outputs to improve the Open Repository for Psychological Research Instruments (REPOPSI)

The EOSCFuture.eu/RDA open calls

The open calls managed by the Research Data Alliance (RDA) with funding from EOSCFuture.eu aim to bring data initiatives closer to EOSC and provide EOSC with expertise, tools, best practices, and standards from the global research data community, with a total million Euro reserved to fund over 65 grantees over 12 open calls.

The Project Involved

REPOPSI was supported under the RDA Open Call for Cross Disciplinary Science Adoption Grants #1 and it was implemented by the Laboratory for Research of Individual Differences at the Faculty of Philosophy of University of Belgrade in Serbia from July 2022 until July 2023.

The key objective of the project was to improve the TRUSTworthiness and FAIRness of the REPOPSI (meta)data by implementing RDA recommendations and other outputs. The project focused on building the technologies needed by the repository to improve its adherence to the principles of User Focus, Sustainability, Findability, and Interoperability. Dissemination and community activities were also undertaken to promote further uptake of RDA outputs.

The Research Community

The REPOPSI community are researchers and students in psychology, but also in other social and behavioural sciences. Moreover, REPOPSI is used in teaching university courses in psychometrics and related fields. As currently half of instrument records are available in both Serbian and English, REPOPSI is useful to both local and international researchers

Aleksandra Lazić

Research Assistant at the University of Belgrade – Faculty of Philosophy, Serbia

“The EOSC Portal and Marketplace have enabled us to showcase our work to a broader user base and establish connections with potential users in new ways. Additionally, EOSC has elevated our visibility and credibility at a European level, with the potential for REPOPSI to make an impact on the global community”

The Challenge

As the first centralised repository for psychological instruments in Serbian, one of the main goals of the project was to prevent duplication of efforts in translating/adapting instruments and to provide a space for local researchers to promote their original instruments. A further challenge was to facilitate easy access to essential materials for researchers and students. While the Open Science Framework - the free platform hosting REPOPSI - is a valuable hosting platform, this also posed challenges in terms of Reusability (e.g. metadata cannot refer to a machine-understandable reuse licence) and Interoperability (e.g. metadata values cannot be expressed using a controlled vocabulary). REPOPSI also had the need to promote its data and services to a wider, global research community.

EOSC service or tool used

The team used the “FAIR Data Maturity Model” and “CoreTrustSeal Requirements 2023-2025” to self-assess FAIRness and TRUSTworthiness at the beginning and at the end of the project. FAIRsharing was used to find a FAIR-compliant controlled vocabulary and a metadata schema that could be applied; from which the Library of Congress Subject Headings and the DataCite Metadata Schema were chosen. Further, REPOPSI was added as a new database record in FAIRsharing and project deliverables are available on Zenodo. REPOPSI is listed in the re3data registry. After registering the institution as a new EOSC Provider, REPOPSI was also added to the EOSC providers hub and can be visited in the EOSC Marketplace [here](#).

Keywords:

#data, #OpenScience, #FAIRprinciples, #FAIRsharing, #FAIRdata #Trust, #FAIR indicators, #EOSCinPractice

Useful tips & tricks

We consulted the following online course while registering our institution as a new EOSC Provider and onboarding REPOPSI as a new EOSC Service: "[For EOSC Providers - Onboarding](#)". In the future, we plan to explore other training resources provided by the EOSC Knowledge Hub (e.g. on how to integrate our service with the EOSC Helpdesk or the EOSC Monitoring Service).

Benefits and impact

The EOSC Portal and Marketplace enable us to showcase REPOPSI to a wider user base and to engage with prospective users in new ways. For example, users can now easily compare REPOPSI to similar services and include it in their EOSC Marketplace Projects, along with other resources of interest. EOSC helps researchers perform better, more efficient and transparent science by making it easier for them to find, share, and reuse open data. In addition, EOSC nurtures a diverse, equal, and inclusive research environment by allowing anyone to browse, discover or contribute to the tools and services. Moreover, researchers and innovators who come from developing countries or regions that have been underrepresented in science are able to demonstrate that their services meet EOSC quality standards, expanding their impact in the global community.

Why do I need RDA?

The project aimed to improve adherence to the principles of User Focus, Sustainability, Findability, and Interoperability and the RDA outputs used were key to its success. Dissemination and community activities were also undertaken to promote further uptake of RDA outputs.

Useful material related to this story

rda-alliance.org

Why do I need EOSC?

The EOSC Marketplace enabled us to browse the research publications and services needed to improve the FAIRness and TRUSTworthiness of our Repository, especially in terms of Reusability and Interoperability, with ease. Ultimately, this allowed us to promote REPOPSI to a more diverse pool of potential users – we could onboard it into EOSC and include it in registered repositories (e.g. FAIRsharing). As the REPOPSI project deliverables are deposited in Zenodo, they can all also be accessed from EOSC. Thanks to its presence in the EOSC Marketplace, REPOPSI can gain more visibility and credibility.

Across disciplines

REPOPSI's structure and documentation as well as the REPOPSI project deliverables are all public and transparent and available in English. Therefore, REPOPSI can serve as a role model for development of other smaller-scale open repositories of existing research data. Furthermore, the methodology developed for REPOPSI can be extended to other scientific domains.

Liked this
#EOSCinPractice
story?

Follow
@EOSCFuture
for more!

